

A Visual Programming Tool for Mobile Web Augmentation

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Abstract

The use of mobile devices for web browsing has increased extraordinarily in recent years becoming the main source of information. Unfortunately, developers cannot meet the needs of all users. As a result, users have been forced to adapt web content to their needs. In addition, users are faced with more costly interactions than on desktop computers due to the smaller screen size of cell phones. These interactions are URL typing, scrolling, tapping, branching and tab-switching. If the number of Web resources is large, the activity becomes unpleasant. Furthermore, should the quantity of interactions be extensive, the web experience also becomes unpleasant. Furthermore, all these interactions lead to higher costs in terms of phone time and battery life, as well as more costly navigation.

Web Augmentation enhances the user web experience by adding content from different resources, modifying the original layout or reducing interactions during web searches, among other benefits. To reduce user interactions and satisfy their information necessities, we propose MAWA, an extension for Firefox mobile that allows to adapt any web page to the user's needs through Web Augmentation techniques. To validate our proposal, an evaluation of the tool has been carried out. The article presents the benefits introduced by MAWA as a response to the inconveniences experienced by users when performing their activities in the mobile browser. The results obtained show that MAWA is able to reduce the number of interactions abruptly, as well as to reduce

battery consumption and the time needed to obtain the desired information. In addition, users perceive that navigation is more uncluttered.

Keywords: Human-Computer Interaction, End-User Development, Web Augmentation, Customization, Mobile Browser

1 Introduction

There has been a substantial rise in the usage of mobile phones in recent decades, which has led to an increase in access to web applications [1]. The number of web users is increasing, as is the number of mobile users [2]. According to various reports, the demand for mobile data will skyrocket in the coming decade [3]. In 1995, Boehm et al. [4] predicted that there would be 55 million Web practitioners in the United States by 2005. Scaffidi et al. [5] predicted in 2005 that there would be 90 million end-users in the United States in 2012. If we extrapolate this amount globally, we can imagine that the real number today is uncountable. In reality, mobile traffic now accounts for more than half of all Internet traffic. End-user participation in website customization according to their needs and preference has increased as a result of this growth [6]. End-users can customize web pages by changing the colors, relocating components, removing features, or adding new elements. In other words, tailor the functionality, content, and design to the user's needs. Since most web users around the world are simple customers with minimal programming expertise, the customization process is primarily performed by users with no programming skills. Web Augmentation (WA) is a common technique for customizing existing third-party websites. Bouvin [7] originally coined the term WA in 1999 to describe a tool that "through integration with a Web browser, a HTTP proxy or a Web server adds content or controls not contained within the Web pages themselves to the effect of allowing structure to be added to the Web page directly or indirectly, or to navigate such structure. The purpose of such a tool is to help users organize, associate, or structure information found on the Web. This activity can be performed by a single user or in collaboration with others". Augmentation is created by the web user, not the website owner. There are multitude of techniques for implementing WA, but one of the most popular is to use visual programming techniques [8]. The use of graphics as a programming language is known as visual programming [9], which facilitates the development of new functionality in websites by end-users.

Lieberman et al. [10] define End-User Development (EUD) as "a set of methods, techniques and tools that allow users of software systems, acting as non-professional software developers, to create, modify or extend a software artefact". End-users may begin with simple adaptation mechanisms and progress to more effective adaptation mechanisms without encountering insurmountable obstacles [11]. WA is an ideal EUD technique because it can be implemented gradually. WA can be used on any website and is carried out by

end-users. Mobile users suffer the same disadvantages as desktop users. Since desktop computers were initially the only supported platform for accessing the Internet, websites were initially designed for them. However, technology has progressed to the point that mobile phones and tablets are now popular platforms for browsing websites using navigation browsers [12]. As a result of this natural evolution, web designers acquired a routine of first designing for desktop computers with high screen resolutions. Subsequently, they would create a mobile-friendly version of the website keeping the same layout [13]. Since mobile versions are often modifications of desktop versions, problems can be increased. WA can be used not only for desktop web versions, but also for mobile web versions, which can be personalized by end-users. When browsing on a mobile device, users need resources and techniques that meet their needs. This paper looks into WA as a mechanism for end-users to customize web pages through a Firefox mobile browser extension for web adaptation.

To accomplish this work we have used the Design Science Research (DSR) methodology [14]. DSR has been defined as "research that invents a new purposeful artifact to address a generalised type of problem and evaluates its utility for solving problems of that type" [15]. The method consists of five steps. The first one is to identify and motivate the problem. "DSR requires a profound understanding of the problem to be solved, the consequences to be alleviated, and the causes to be prevented" [16]. The next step in DSR is to define the objectives of the solution, which in most cases is accomplished through the development of some tool or application. The objectives always try to alleviate some of the consequences of the problem or to prevent some of its causes [16]. Section 2 defines the problem, its causes, consequences and objectives. The third step of the DSR method is the design and development of the tool or application to be developed. The fourth step consists of demonstrating by means of real cases that the developed tool meets the objectives. Section 3 shows steps 3 and 4 and illustrates them by means of a real example. It describes MAWA¹ (Mobile Application for Web Augmentation), a browser extension that customizes mobile version web pages to adapt them to users requirements. Lastly, step 5 of the DSR consists of evaluating the developed tool by people not involved in the development. The objective of the evaluation is to demonstrate that the defined objectives are met. Section 4 shows the conducted evaluation. If any of the steps 3, 4 or 5 did not meet the defined objectives, the DSR proposes to go back to step 2. The DSR is an iterative process that ends when the defined objectives are satisfied. Section 5 discusses related work in order to give the reader an idea of what has been done in this area. Finally, section 6 shows features we would like to enhance about MAWA and concludes the paper.

¹<https://addons.mozilla.org/es/firefox/addon/mawa/>

2 Problem statement

2.1 The problem

At the beginning, all websites were designed only for desktops, but with the introduction of web browsing on mobile phones, this started to change. The process of web browsing on cell phones was quite cumbersome and developers were designing two different versions of the same website, one for desktop and the other for mobile phones. However, technologies are changing and the Mobile First principle is an increasingly widespread concept. Mobile First is a philosophy developed by Luke Wroblewski [17], which points to prioritize the mobile environment over the desktop.

Mobile First is the practice of developing a website design from its most basic form by first approaching it for the small screen of a Smartphone from an iterative growth, provides an instance for other higher resolution devices[17]. Nonetheless, a large number of web designers still design their initial web development for desktop resolution and subsequently, design the adaptation to the mobile paradigm[18]. The desktop version design first causes problems and disadvantages to the mobile web browser edition [3].

The process of transforming a web depending on the screen resolution is carried out with Responsive Web Design (RWD). RWD is a design and implementation technique that enables web designers and developers to create websites with a flexible approach to adapt their content and layout to different resolutions on different devices with the same web experience [19]. Yet, this reorganization is not free, a computational cost is included by having to adapt the initial desktop version to the mobile browser configuration. Moreover, this adaptation causes usability problems such as displaying unnecessary content, reordering of important content and, as a consequence, cluttered navigation and scrolling to find the desired information, among others [20]. These usability drawbacks induce a poor web experience for users.

RWD was created for desktop-to-mobile adaptation and not vice versa even though it is common to listen that it should be "mobile first design" [21], RWD avoids creating two different versions of the same website (desktop and mobile versions). Nevertheless, in order to satisfy all user necessities, web developers should develop a version for each user. This is completely unfeasible, each individual has different needs, hobbies or interests. A very common technique to adapt the content to user preferences is web personalization. "Web personalization is an automated process that identifies a user, collects his or her navigation patterns, analyzes known preferences of similar users, and estimates his or her specific preferences to tailor content for each user" [22]. However, personalization techniques can not always foresee individual practices. The WA technique is best suited to the user's needs.

2.2 Causes

The reasons why it is unviable to develop a web version for each user and the RWD implementation are:

- **No cost effective:** web development companies are not interested in developing a personal software or a different version for each user. The reason is that the more clients you have, the more versions you will implement. The cost of producing these personal web versions would be unacceptable for companies.
- **Not easy to foresee:** it is impossible to develop a web design that provides information for every situation or includes personalized information for every user [23]. There are applications that automate and personalize web interactions [24][25]. However, these tools are insufficient to guarantee the achievement of user objectives when updates to the relevant context cannot be fully anticipated at design time [26].
- **User effort:** if web developers are not interested in creating different web versions to fulfill everybody's requirements, end-users are obliged to perform this task. End-users do not have programming knowledge and the effort they required to make web adaptations with programming languages is tremendous. One of the goals of end-user augmentation tools is the reduction of the effort of end-users to adapt their websites and therefore the gulf of execution [27].
- **Small screen:** There has been different research studies that have investigated the issues due to the screen size and its effects. [28] concluded that small screen size might be the reason why users contribute with lower quality data when using mobile phones compared to desktop computer users responding to questionnaires. [29] compared error proneness depending on the screen size and their results indicate that larger device size leads to better authentication rates. [30] concluded that screen size affects both readability and comprehension. [31] deduced that people who view a small portion of a website often lack a sense of the overall context. Additionally, they extrapolated that users feel lost on a large page and that they are forced to remember the locations of desired web elements and scroll to view them.

2.3 Consequences

The consequences of the invalidity to develop a web version for each user and the RWD implementation are:

- **Scroll:** [32] conducted a study in which they determined that people used the scroll bar on 76% of pages, and 22% scrolled to the bottom regardless of the length of the page. A frequent action in browsing is to scroll up and down a page without reading the content [33]. This might be a signal of frustration and lack of confidence [33]. In fact, Lagun et. al. [34] concluded that users are less satisfied when they frequently scroll to find irrelevant information in their navigation. Taking into account that, "the current scrolling method

for a mobile device is both time-consuming and fatigue-prone” [35], it is mandatory to reduce scrolling on mobile devices.

- **Taps:** is the action of clicking on a web element on the mobile screen and it requires only a very small scale of device movement (of the order of 1 mm) and can be performed with the finger or palm of the hand [36]. If a user accomplishes a high number of taps, it is a sign of problems [33]. For example, it has been studied that users effectuate more taps than necessary in search tasks and this is due to the tendency of users to make unnecessary clicks [37]. The more clicks the user makes, the worse the interaction. Additionally, taps on mobile devices produce errors in the interaction depending on how the user holds the device [38].
- **Tab-switching:** taking into account that users switch tabs at least 57.4% of the time [39], it is extremely important to reduce this quantity. One way to obtain information from websites in different tabs is constant tab-switching. Nevertheless, if users have to switch tabs to locate previously found information, they do not actually aspire to gather information from these sites [40]. Another study concluded that misplacing a few tabs in the wrong window or tab can have adverse consequences, such as missing important information buried in the wrong task [41]. When multiple activities are involved, it is mandatory to memorize and understand the information contained in each tab [42].
- **Branching:** is defined as the act of initiating a new tab (or window), which allows people to pleasantly navigate multiple websites concurrently [43]. However, this concurrent navigation is not free. [41] concluded that if the number of open tabs increases, users find it more difficult to find relevant information or identify which tabs to focus on. Moreover, they deduced that on average, users have 8 tabs opened and 66,9% of the subjects have one or more issues every week due to the number of tabs opened. Users frequently suspend, resume, and interleave actions that involve managing a large number of tabs in mobile browsing [44].
- **URL typing:** There are some studies that have analyzed the errors when typing a URL [45]. ”Users prefer the former way because typing on screen-limited devices is difficult and chances of entering the wrong URL are high” [46]. It is important to remark that the difficulty of typing a specific domain name or the probability of making a certain type of mistake is not purely random [45].
- **Battery consumption:** is an important topic in mobile usage. Despite the fact that battery life expectancy has increased, users have increased the use of these devices more specially the use of social networks [47]. The activities that consume the most energy are social networking, gaming and searching on the internet [48]. Mobile phone components consume different amounts of energy [49] but the screen consumes the most, about 35% of the device’s total power consumption [50]. Reducing the time the screen is lit and internet searches are essential to reduce battery consumption.

- **Time:** closely related to the previous topic, the faster the user obtains his desired information, the better, because device usage will be reduced. Nonetheless, there are some aspects in which WA cannot act. For example, the web page load time that depends on search loops, file writing and page loading via HTTPS takes between 7 and 13 seconds [51]. The second is that there is a relation between server location and the time it takes to load a web page in a country. In their study, for European countries, the average was 4.72 seconds and for the USA, it was 7.64 seconds. However, the bottleneck of modern browsers was the network connection, which is no longer the bottleneck of the browser [52].
- **Produce cluttered navigation:** the website structure is adapted from the desktop version to mobile version by rearranging the layout and content to the screen resolution [12]. The process of adapting the website generates different disadvantages such as the impediment of reading the content correctly from the device [53]. This drawback produces more user interactions on mobile devices than for desktop users and consequently the time needed to perform any task is more elevated [54]. Furthermore, it causes more input errors than using desktop navigation [55].
- **Show unnecessary content and hide important content:** The main characteristic of RWD is the relocation of the content displayed in the desktop version hiding some content and maintaining others visible in the mobile version [19]. Unfortunately, the displayed content might be useless to users and what is more, if the desired content is concealed, the user must interact with the website to find the necessary information. On some occasions, the simplest action is for the user to have to scroll to find the information. Considering that all mobile web users want to extract the desired information quickly and with minimal mental effort [56], it is compulsory to get the content right.
- **Computational cost reordering content:** RWD techniques modify the appearance of the web page to adapt to the display limitations of a device. Reordering the layout implies a computational cost due to rendering [57]. The problem is that, on some occasions, page layout failures can occur when the page is rendered for different display port sizes. The main drawback is the difficulty of validating all possible layouts [58].

Our initial objective is to develop a tool that alleviates all the consequences outlined in this section. This is an ambitious objective, moreover, considering that the tool should be usable by end-users too.

3 Augmenting Mobile Websites

Nowadays it is more common to use mobile phone browsers than desktop browsers². Therefore, it is of utmost importance to adapt mobile version websites to the needs of users by avoiding or minimizing scrolling, tab-switching, branching, battery consumption, etc. We will illustrate the use of MAWA with

²<https://gs.statcounter.com/platform-market-share/desktop-mobile-tablet>

an example based on the BBC website.

MAWA is a Firefox mobile browser extension for WA designed to remove, move and add content from any website through a visual programming environment. MAWA abstracts technical details into a visual DSL that facilitates end-user involvement. The goal of this extension is to avoid the cause and consequences presented in section 2. Move, remove and add content are the actions that help avoiding the causes and consequences. The new contribution presented in this paper has numerous differences with those presented at the INTERACT2021 conference [59]. For the conference, a very early state of MAWA was presented in which only deleting and moving content from a web page was possible.

Today very few mobile browsers allow you to install extensions (Firefox and Safari are the most popular). Although Firefox is used at 0.6%³, it can be used on both Android and iOS. In the related work it can be seen that the mobile extensions have been developed for Firefox and not for other browsers due to this reason.

3.1 First steps

In general, the number of interactions that a user must carry out in a mobile phone browser is more than in desktop computer browsers [60]. For example, due to the smaller screen size, users must scroll to find desired information in mobile phones even if this info is at the top of the website. Responsive Web Design compacts web menus and users must tap on the menu button before selecting the option. This is why it is mandatory to simplify interactions as much as possible in the extensions. Desktop computer browser extensions are shown in the top left and tapping on it and selecting the menu option, the extension is enacted. Nonetheless, mobile browser extensions are hidden and the user must select the browser menu, the complements, the concrete complement and finally the menu option. Four interactions versus two. Taking all this into account, a simple interaction to show the menu is necessary. Double-tapping is not a popular mobile phone interaction. For that reason, our proposal is that double-tapping on the screen enacts the menu with the different options the user can accomplish (see figure 1). Options deactivated are in grey and each button has its own colour. Only coloured buttons can be tapped. Tapping on the "Cancel" button, the user can continue navigating normally. "New" button activates the WA process. "Mineit" button can be used to copy a web node from the website in which it has been activated. Once the WA process is complete an activated "Save" button would save the adaptation and "Remove" button would eliminate the saved adaptation.

However, browser extension's menus are not the only drawback, node selection is not a basic action in web mobile web browsers. Web programmers are familiar with DOM structure and how it is organized. Nonetheless, end-users do not have the knowledge about how the DOM is organized. WA extensions are designed for users with no technical knowledge and they must be able to complete any action permitted by the extension.

³<https://gs.statcounter.com/browser-market-share/mobile/worldwide>

Fig. 1 Mobile extension menu for Web Augmentation

In order to perform end-user node selection, we have included four buttons, one button on top, one at the bottom and one at each side of the selected node (see figure 2). Any node can be selected by tapping on it, but some nodes cannot be selected simply by tapping on it due to their peculiarities. Added arrows permit selecting selected relative nodes. For example, the figure 2 left image has a weather image node selected in the BBC website. Left arrow permits selecting the previous node and the right arrow is used to select the next brother. If we tap on the arrow button on top of the selected node, the father node is selected (figure 2 right). The right image in figure 2 includes an arrow button at the bottom. The first child is selected when the user taps on the bottom arrow button. If the selected node does not have any children, this button is hidden (figure 2 left). For the same reason, if the selected node does not have a previous or any following brother, these buttons are also hidden. Top button is only hidden when the body node is selected.

This mechanism permits selecting any interactive node indirectly. Furthermore, nodes bigger than screen mobile screen resolution can be selected by tapping on the top arrow button and even complete tables can be selected utilizing the same process. Thanks to this mechanism any node can be selected.

Fig. 2 Node selection including relatives buttons: leaf node (left), leaf node father (right)

WA can be accomplished even difficultly selectable nodes are involved in the augmentation.

3.2 Move

The first action implemented in MAWA is moving web nodes from one position to another one. The main goal of moving content is to avoid scrolling. Every website has its own structure designed by the web designer although this structure might not fit with all user requirements. Imagine that a user always reads the "World in pictures" section in the BBC website which is at the bottom of the website. The user must scroll all the website until the bottom to read this section although he would like to have it at the top. MAWA allows moving this node to the top always. This is done by dragging and dropping the selected node. When the node is dragged, the background colour where the node could be dropped becomes purple. This colour transformation provides the user with information as to what the new location of the node might be. Once the node is dropped, it is inserted into its new locations and hidden from the original position. The reason to hide the element is that the copy is updated with the last real content. Figure 3 shows on the left (A) a selected

Fig. 3 Moving a node from the bottom to the top of the BBC website

node by the user with the "World in pictures" section in the BBC website. The same figure in the middle (B) shows how the user is relocating the node to the top of the website in which the background of the node where it is going to be inserted is purple. Figure 3 shows in the right (C) the node inserted at the top of the website. This figure demonstrates with an example how MAWA helps to avoid scrolling in case essential or important information is at the bottom and, consequently, also to avoid cluttered navigation.

3.3 Remove

The second action implemented in MAWA is the removal of unnecessary nodes for the user. The main goal of this action is to prevent the user from consuming unnecessary content that the web designer thought would be useful. Websites might present information that is not relevant to the user. This information may not be annoying on desktop computer screens, however, it is frustrating when consumed on small cell phone screens [54] [55].

Continuing with the BBC example, imagine that the user hates sports and therefore, this information is useless for the user. The best solution would be to remove this content from the site. If the user decides to remove this node, the user must click the X button located in the upper right corner of the selected node (figure 4 left). Once clicked, the node is removed from the web page (figure 4 right). Henceforth, every time the user reloads or revisits the website, this node would be hidden, simplifying the website content. Thus, MAWA is eluding cluttered navigation besides avoiding that the user consumes unnecessary content.

Fig. 4 Removing a node from the BBC website

3.4 Inserting foreign content

Not only is node relocation and removal a solution to mitigate the problems and consequences shown in section 2, but also adding content from different resources is a method that mitigates these drawbacks. We can differentiate two types of foreign content: the constant node which content does not need to be updated and the one that needs to bring up to date.

The creation process is the same for both. When a user visits a website and he double-taps on the screen, the extension menu shows the option "MineIT" (see figure 1). Once the user clicks on it, the creation process starts. Equally to the editing process to move and remove web nodes, when the user taps on a web element, the background of the node changes the colour. The difference is that this node contains a button in the middle with the word "COPY" (see figure 5 left). If the user clicks on this button, MAWA demands the user inserts a name to this copied element to complete the creation process. When the user clicks on "Accept", the page is reloaded and the element saved. Clicking on "Cancel", the creation process finishes but the element is not saved (see figure 5 right).

The main goal of inserting content from different websites is to avoid or reduce the number of taps, tab-switching, branching and URL typing. Most users visit a second website to complete their user experience [24]. If the consumed content is inserted automatically in the initial website, branching is eluded and as a consequence URL typing. Furthermore, the user does not need to change the tab because everything is in the same tab preventing from tab switching. This reduction on tab actions reduces drastically the quantity of taps accomplished by the user.

Fig. 5 Mining a web node

Fig. 6 List of nodes copied from different websites

3.4.1 Updating content

Some nodes' content must be upgraded because their nature is dynamic and the content is updated by the website owner frequently. When the user wants to insert a node, he must tap on the "+" button that is constantly on the top right of the screen. Figure 6 shows the list of copied components after tapping on the "+" button. The list can be hidden by clicking on the "-" button on the top right. To insert the element the user must tap on the element he wants to insert and tap on a web element to insert it after this element. Figure 7 left shows how the user has inserted the program of the BBC channel from a TV guide⁴. The BBC channel schedule is updated every hour and the user would like the last version content every time he visits the site. This new element contains two different buttons. At the right the "X" can be used to remove the element. At the left, the "Constant/Update" button defines if this element must be updated or not. Figure 7 right shows the element with the background in green which means that this element will be updated every time the user visits this website. Notice that the content of this button changes from "Constant" to "Update" depending on the state.

3.4.2 Constant content

There are some nodes that will be constant. This means that the information it contains is important for the user and it must not be updated even if it could

⁴<https://www.tvguide.co.uk/>

Fig. 7 Updating content from foreign element

Fig. 8 Constant content from foreign element

be upgraded in the original site. Finishing with the BBC example, imagine that a non English speaker desires translating some piece of news to his language. Figure 8 shows how the user has inserted the DeepL content to the top of the website facilitating the access to this website. This content must be always the same independently the day.

3.5 General improvements

MAWA provides three different actions (move, remove and add) that have been designed to diminish or avoid the causes and consequences of the problem presented in section 2. These actions were designed to avoid or diminish these drawbacks directly (scrolling, hiding unnecessary content, taping, tab-switching, branching and URL typing). Nevertheless, MAWA has been designed to prevent the other disadvantages. Cluttered navigation is avoided due to node removal and content relocation owing to the fact the user adapts site's content to his necessities. MAWA as a whole, tries to diminish the effects of the causes. Now, it is possible to have a different version for users of the same website making it easy even if the website owner is not involved in the edition. The visual programming interface has been designed to facilitate the adaptation by end-users, users with no programming knowledge, diminishing the effort to adapt any website. Nevertheless, it is impossible to change the small screen resolution of mobile phones. In addition, the computational cost reordering content consequence is not avoided because MAWA does not remove RWD operations. What is more, it adds some computational cost to reorder the added, moved and removed nodes. In order to confirm these statements, an evaluation has been carried out.

3.6 Data model

WA process with MAWA is divided in two different phases: the editing phase and the execution phase. The data model has been designed taking into account the information the system must store in both phases. The editing phase saves the actions performed by the end-user and the execution process gets this previously saved information and MAWA uses it to execute the WA. We take advantage of the browser structure to store this information in it. The data model is illustrated in figure 9.

Every augmentation performed by MAWA is registered by an ID created exclusively for it. Additionally, it saves the URL in which the augmentation will be executed. When the end-user introduces a new URL or reloads a web page, MAWA's engine checks whether this URL has been used in an augmentation. If this URL is saved in the system, it starts the whole process to accomplish the augmentation. Otherwise, the system waits until another web page is loaded. It is important to remark that MAWA allows to have more than one adaptation to the same domain. MAWA is enacted only when the current URL is the same as it was at design time.

Each augmentation will be composed by one or more nodes that will be modified or inserted in the editing process. All nodes are identified by an unique ID. Each node's information is completed with its location point on the page and the actions that MAWA will complete when the augmentation is enacted. The location point is formed by a locator, a Xpath. A Web locator can be defined as a mechanism for uniquely identifying an element in the Document Object Model (DOM) [61]. This locator provides information about the location of the node from the website that will be moved or removed. Nodes

Fig. 9 MAWA data model

inserted from foreign websites do not need the location point information to complete their action.

There are three different actions and MAWA must save the appropriate information to complete all of them. The Xpath is used to locate the position in which the moved node and the inserted nodes will be inserted. It will be empty when the node is removed because the location point provides this information. Visible attribute is used for removed elements and moved ones. When an element is moved, a copy is inserted in the new location and the original one is hidden. If an update in the content of this node has been carried out, the user will see the updated content and not the old one. This is the reason why the HTML attribute is empty for move and remove and it is used to save the HTML code of foreign nodes only. The update attribute provides information if the HTML must be updated or not. If this is true, the Update's URL provides the website in which the new HTML content must be captured with the information provided by the Xpath locator.

In previous subsections, mainly it has been explained the editing process from

the actions implemented in MAWA. However, this editing process is the previous step to the execution process. This process's goal is to reproduce the user's creation steps one by one. For this reason, MAWA saves information about each modification made by the user in the editing process following the data model described. The automation process finds the first modified element and reproduces the user's actions by deleting and relocating all nodes. This process continues until the last edited node in the same order as the user followed in the editing steps. However, every foreign element, if it must be updated, it is upgraded in parallel. It does not matter how many elements must be updated, the execution time would be the time needed to update the slowest website. It also will depend on the connection speed. At the end, the layout will be the same one the user had at the end of the editing process. The main drawbacks of the automation process are website updates. Website updates can cause MAWA to not be able to find the modifiable nodes. As a consequence, automation fails. This failure can occur in three different cases. The first is when the node to be deleted or moved has been deleted from the website or relocated. The locator (mechanism used to locate nodes within a website) is not able to find the node. In this case, if the node is to be deleted, the user does not perceive any error. Nevertheless, if the node is to be moved, the user may notice that an important element is missing. The second case is when the node selected as reference to relocate the node has been removed or relocated. In this case, the system is not able to relocate the node and it seems that the node simply has been removed from the website. The third case is when the website from which MAWA has to extract an updated content has been updated and this update affects the element. In this occasion, the system inserts a message of failure instead of the element itself (see figure 10). If one of these cases occurs, the end-user could update the adaptation by double-tapping on the screen and selecting update.

4 Evaluation

We have conducted two types of user tests for the evaluation of MAWA. A quantitative evaluation in which we user actions in a real task in their daily life and the actions they accomplish doing the same activity with MAWA. The actions measured are the quantitative ones reported in causes and consequences described in section 2. A qualitative evaluation in which subjects carried out a guided activity using MAWA and we collected qualitative data. We utilized a standard questionnaire to collect this data PSSUQ (Post-Study System Usability Questionnaire) and general questions based on the causes and consequences explained in section 2. PSSUQ [62] assesses user satisfaction after participation in an instrument evaluation.

Fig. 10 Failure updating a foreign element

4.1 Quantitative evaluation

This section of the evaluation appraises the causes and consequences of section 2 that can be evaluated quantitatively (scrolling, taping, tab-switching, branching, URL typing, battery consumption, execution time and rendering).

4.1.1 Battery consumption

AccuBattery⁵ application has been used to measure the energy consumption. This application is able to measure the energy consumption by application starting from a charged mobile or when it is switched on. Each execution has been carried out when the mobile phone was completely charged.

Figure 11 left shows the battery consumption by Firefox applications executing the BBC example with MAWA, the same example described in section 3. On the contrary, figure 11 right shows the battery consumption of Firefox to execute the natural steps to perform the same action without MAWA. The battery consumption with MAWA have been 1.5mAh whereas the battery consumption without MAWA 12.1mAh. This means that MAWA reduces the battery consumption 8 times more than performing the same content consumption without MAWA. This means that MAWA reduces the battery consumption a 87.6%.

⁵<https://play.google.com/store/apps/details?id=com.digibites.accubattery>

Fig. 11 (Left) Battery consumption with MAWA, (right) battery consumption without MAWA

4.1.2 Computational cost reordering content

The Firefox Developer Tool Inspector has been used to measure the time needed to render the website layout. This tool allows recording the execution time of the different aspects of a web page loading such as the rendering, loading or scripting. Each execution is not exactly the same and the time needed to load is different. This is the reason why it has been executed the BBC example 20 times with and without MAWA in order to obtain a more exact rendering execution time. The average rendering time without MAWA has been 815,7ms. The average rendering time with MAWA has been 891,95ms. The difference with and without MAWA is 76,25ms, 9,18% of increment. We can consider that the difference is short enough to be considered irrelevant from the user perspective.

4.1.3 Diminishing user interactions and consumption

The aim is to compare the same information consumption on the web with and without MAWA and measure the reduction of interactions and resources consumption.

Research Method

Settings. The study was conducted in Mondragon University (Arrasate - Mondragon, Spain). All participants used their own mobile phones in which they had installed Firefox Browser (Nightly for Developers). This browser permits the installation of Firefox extensions.

Procedure. At the beginning, subjects were evaluated one by one and they did not know anything about the purpose of the activity. They only knew that they were going to be monitored in a task they do frequently, which was decided by them at the moment. Next day, they were demanded to use MAWA to complete the same task and they were monitored again. The example consisted of adding content to a national TV guide website from filmaffinity, rottentomatoes and a TV guide website. Additionally, they had to remove channels they do not like and relocate to the top their favourite channels. Next, participants were proposed to adapt another website they visit frequently. This day, each subject was explained how to use MAWA. The reason to do the second part next day was that users forget the results from previous day and it is enough time to remember what they did the previous day.

Subjects. Five use cases were performed by 20 end-users, who did not have any programming knowledge skills. Each subject works in a different economic sectors; research, medicine, sales, plumbing, driver, etc.

Instrument. Each subject completed the activity alone and by his own while a reviewer captured each action performed in the activity. We measured scroll, taps, tab-switching, URL typing, branching, time, battery consumption and computational cost reordering content. These are the quantitative measurements identified in section 2:

Results

The evaluation results are summarized in table 1 and table 2. All issues in both tables refer to consequences described in section 2. During the evaluation, a reviewer wrote down every single action accomplished by the subjects with and without MAWA. Table 1 shows in the first five columns the number of each action performed by subjects in their activity without using MAWA. Battery consumption and rendering cost have been calculated independently after the user activity was finished in the same manner explained in subsections 4.1.1 and 4.1.2. The last column calculates the time needed to conclude the activity. Conversely, table 2 shows the actions performed by the subjects in the same activity using MAWA. The battery consumption, rendering cost and time have been calculated in the same manner. First group of users compare the same product in different websites such as book price in Amazon and Powell's. Second group looks for information relative to a journey they will do in the near future. Third group searches for information relative to movies before selecting one. Fourth group are keen on sports and they look for information related to their favourite one. Last group of users search for information relative to gossip and yellow press.

During the activity, the reviewer annotated every single action accomplished by the subjects. Tab-switching is taken into account when the user changes the tab, taps when the user touches the screen to click on a web element, scrolling when he scrolls to find information that is not at the initial position of the website. Branching is opening a new tab and with URL typing the user introduces an URL in the tab. These actions are related because when the user opens a new tab he introduces a new URL. In some occasions, the user introduces the URL in an opened tab but in most occasions, a new tab was opened. Finally, the time measures the time needed to complete the activity in seconds. Battery consumption and rendering cost have been calculated in the same manner explained in subsections 4.1.1 and 4.1.2.

Comparing tables 1 and 2, it is noticeable that the number of actions and values of all columns (with the exception of the rendering cost) has decreased significantly for all use cases when they use MAWA. First five columns represent the actions performed by a user. First use case (UC1 in tables 1 and 2) actions without MAWA were 49.1 and 1.4 with MAWA. This is a reduction of 97,15% in the number of actions. Second use case (UC2 in tables 1 and 2) reduces the number of actions from 53.9 to 2.8 (a reduction of 94,8%). Third use case (UC3 in tables 1 and 2) passes from 33.6 to 1.6 actions (95,23%). The fourth use case (UC4 in tables 1 and 2) executed 34.7 actions without MAWA and 1.6 with MAWA (95,39%). Finally, UC5, last row in tables 1 and 2 performed 43.5 actions without MAWA and 2.5 with MAWA (a reduction

of 94.25%). To sum up, the number of actions have been reduced by 95.39% (from 214.8 to 9.9). Regarding battery consumption, in total, all use cases have consumed 142.2mAh when they do not use MAWA and 10.3mAh with MAWA. This means a reduction of 92.75% in the energy consumption. As for rendering cost, the total cost has been 6014 milliseconds without MAWA and 6566 milliseconds with MAWA. This means that the rendering cost is a 9.18% more elevated with the extension than without MAWA. Finally, the time to finish the task is 84.83% lower (822.222 seconds without MAWA versus 124.704 seconds with MAWA).

The quantitative evaluation confirms that some of the consequences of the problem described in section 2 are solved or mitigated by MAWA. The number of user interactions decreased a 95.39%, the execution time was 84.83% and battery consumption was 92.75%. Nevertheless, rendering cost is 9.18% more elevated. Although the increase in rendering makes battery consumption higher, the drastic reduction in execution time makes battery consumption much lower. Taking into account the benefits obtained in the other issues, the increase of the rendering time in approximately 100 milliseconds is acceptable. Subsections 4.1.1 and 4.1.2 affirm that results calculated to the BBC example explained in the article are very similar to those calculated in the use cases evaluation.

Table 1 Number of actions completed by users in mobile phones without MAWA

Without MAWA								
	Scroll	Tap	Tab-switching	Branching	URL typing	Battery consumption	Rendering cost	Time
UC1	11.9	22.6	8.5	3.3	2.8	25.2	1356	162.334
UC2	15.1	20.5	9.7	4.6	4.0	33.6	1129	201.658
UC3	8.4	15.3	6.3	2.2	1.4	22.8	1533	122.419
UC4	9.3	11.8	7.7	3.1	2.8	32.1	969	149.287
UC5	11.2	17.3	8.1	3.8	3.1	28.5	1027	186.524

4.2 Qualitative evaluation

This section of the evaluation appraises all the causes and consequences of section 2.

Research Method

Settings. The study was conducted in Mondragon University (Arrasate - Mondragon, Spain). All participants used their own mobile phones due to Covid19 measurements in which they had installed the Firefox Nightly app.

Procedure. At the very beginning of the evaluation, participants were

Table 2 Number of actions completed by users in mobile phones with MAWA

With MAWA								
	Scroll	Tap	Tab-switching	Branching	URL typing	Battery consumption	Rendering cost	Time
UC1	1.2	0.2	0	0	0	1.7	1518	20.112
UC2	2.4	0.4	0	0	0	2.6	1234	32.913
UC3	1.4	0.2	0	0	0	1.6	1621	22.025
UC4	1.6	0	0	0	0	2.4	1102	26.357
UC5	2.5	0	0	0	0	2.0	1091	23.297

informed of the purpose of the study and were given a brief description of it. Thereupon, a video with a MAWA instance was presented to exemplify the main functionality of the application. The example consisted of adding content to a national TV guide website from filmaffinity, rottentomatoes and a TV guide website. Additionally, they had to remove channels they do not like and relocate to the top their favourite channels. Next, participants were proposed to adapt another website they visit frequently. Finally, the participants were directed to a Google Forms on-line questionnaire.

Subjects. Twenty four people took part in the evaluation and 75% of the participants were male. Participants were from Arrasate-Mondragon and the nearby towns. Nobody had technical knowledge, the aim of the evaluation was to test MAWA with end-users. All participants were between 18 and 39 years old. 70,8% of participants have installed at least one extension in their mobile phone browser. 54,2% of the participants visit more than 5 web pages in their mobile every day and only one subject does not use the phone to surf the net everyday. 54,2% of the subjects have more than 6 tabs opened each session in their mobile phone and no one has only one tab opened. 70,8% of the participants spend more than 30 minutes everyday on the net with their phones.

Instrument. In order to gather users' experience in the evaluation, a questionnaire was utilized. The questionnaire was composed of the sections; background, usability (PSSUQ questionnaire) and general questions related to the causes and consequences of the section 2. General questions were measured using different questions with a 7-point Likert scale (1=completely disagree, 7=completely agree).

Data Analysis. Descriptive statistics have been used to characterize the sample and to evaluate the participants' experience using MAWA.

4.2.1 PSSUQ

PSSUQ questionnaire is widely used to evaluate the usability of a tool. PSSUQ is used to measure the usability with 16 questions. This usability scale has

been used in this evaluation because we wanted to know the global usability assessment from the user's perspective about MAWA. The questionnaire is done by averaging three sub-scales; System Quality (the average of items 1-6), Information Quality (the average of items 7-12), and Interface Quality (the average of items 13-16) [63]. It uses a 7-point Likert scale (1=completely disagree, 7=completely agree) and an additional with a NA option. PSSUQ question results are reported in Table 3 and summarized in the figure 12.

With regard to the System Quality question, all average values are between 2 and 3 with the exception of the fifth question that is below 2. It is possible to affirm that subjects believe that MAWA is first rate in quality. They claim that it is easy to use (Q1 AVG 2,16) and simple to use (Q2 AVG 2,21). The worst value has been 5 and 4 respectively and few participants voted so high. In their opinion, users were able to complete the activity quickly (Q3 AVG 2,58) and they were comfortable using the extension (Q4 AVG 2,71). Finally, users affirm that MAWA is easy to learn (Q5 AVG 1,71) and that they will be productive using the tool (Q6 AVG 2,66).

As for the Information Quality, some values are also between 2 and 3 with the exception of question 7 which in this occasion is a bit higher than 3 and questions 9 and 10 which are below 2. Results support that MAWA's Information Quality is excellent. Question 7 asks about the appropriate messaging of errors. MAWA provides information about element extraction failures. However, being the worst valued usability aspect, this feature should be improved (Q7, AVG 3,04). Recovering previous versions after a mistake using the tool is correctly valued by subjects (Q8 AVG 2,46). The information provided about the extension was appropriate (Q9 AVG 1,96) and it was easy to find information needed (Q10 AVG 1,96). Additionally, the information provided to complete the activity was correct in their opinion (Q11 AVG 2,37). Finally, the screen information is suitable in their opinion (Q12 AVG 2,33).

As far as the Interface quality is concerned, all results are between 2 and 3. Hence, it is possible to affirm that participants found the interface outstanding. In general, they found the interface pleasant (Q13 AVG 2,66) and they liked to use the interface (Q14 AVG 2,83). Subjects thought that MAWA provides all the functionalities it might have in a tool with these characteristics (Q15 AVG 2,95). Finally, all were satisfied with the system (Q16 AVG 2,08). Standard deviation measures the amount of variation or dispersion of a set of values. The lower the value, the more values are near the average value. Most values are close to the 1 value, which means that most subjects' opinion are similar. The lowest standard deviation value is for Q10 because most subjects thought it was easy to find the information needed in the provided document. One of the reasons might be that all subjects' opinion were below 3 (the lowest maximum value of the questionnaire). The second standard deviation below 1 is the Q5, which affirms that for most subjects MAWA is easy to use. Most values are between 1 and 2 and the median is 1,5. The most elevated standard deviations are in Q7 and Q13, those two questions with the maximum value with 7. The reason is that the opinion for these issues is more diverse.

Fig. 12 PSSUQ scores**Table 3** PSSUQ results

	AVG	Med	SD	Max	Min
Q1	2,16	2	1,2	5	1
Q2	2,21	2	1,18	4	1
Q3	2,58	3	1,38	5	1
Q4	2,71	2,5	1,3	6	1
Q5	1,71	1,5	0,85	4	1
Q6	2,66	2,5	1,4	6	1
Q7	3,04	3	1,57	7	1
Q8	2,46	2,5	1,02	4	1
Q9	1,96	1,5	1,16	4	1
Q10	1,92	2	0,72	3	1
Q11	2,37	2	1,21	4	1
Q12	2,33	2	1,37	6	1
Q13	2,66	2,5	1,55	7	1
Q14	2,83	2,5	1,46	6	1
Q15	2,95	3	1,37	5	1
Q16	2,08	2	1,1	4	1

4.2.2 General questions

Before the general questions, in the background section of the questionnaire, subjects were asked about some of the causes and consequences of section 2. 83,3% of the subject must always scroll before finding something of their interest in the mobile phone. They consider that in 54,4% of the websites they visit, there is unnecessary content and in the 50% of the websites interesting content is hidden due to the RWD. They consider that in 58,3% of the websites, they have problems finding their desired information. 62,5% of them claim that mobile browsing is really complex. The battery life is lower than

Fig. 13 Question scores

1 day for 66,7% of the subjects. In general, they affirm that they perform a large number of clicks, they have a large number of tabs opened and they are continuously tab-switching in their mobile browser operations. They also consider that they accomplish mistakes writing by hand and memory the website's URLs. Finally, they assert that mobile browsing is more complex that desktop computer browsing and that the small screen size of mobile phones is a drawback for browsing.

General question results are reported in Table 4 and summarized in the figure 13. In this questionnaire a Likert scale is used from 1 to 7. These questions evaluate subjects' feelings about the influence of MAWA mitigating or eliminating the causes and the consequences of the problem described in section 2. The more causes and consequences are solved, the more influence of MAWA in solving the problem. Questions 1 to 4 are about the causes and questions 5 and 14 about the consequences described in section 2.

For this questionnaire, it has been a 7-point Likert scale (1=completely disagree, 7=completely agree). Questions have been written to discover if MAWA solves or helps to diminish their effect on mobile browsing.

- Q1 No cost effective: in the subject's opinion, it is not possible economically to develop a different version of the same website for every user. However, they affirm that MAWA would help in having different versions of the same website. Subject's opinion is 2,25 in average, a median of 2 with a maximum value of 5 and a minimum of 1.
- Q2 Not easy to foresee: participants' opinion is 2,58 with a median of 3, a maximum vote of 4 and a minimum of 1 related to this topic. They consider that MAWA facilitates adding content to any website. The web developer

Table 4 Question results

	AVG	Med	SD	Max	Min
Q1	2,25	2	1,15	5	1
Q2	2,58	3	1,02	4	1
Q3	2,45	2	1,21	6	1
Q4	1,62	1	0,88	3	1
Q5	1,71	1	0,95	4	1
Q6	2,37	2	1,06	5	1
Q7	1,58	1,5	0,65	3	1
Q8	2,12	2	1,03	4	1
Q9	2,79	3	1,17	5	1
Q10	2,71	3	1,33	6	1
Q11	2,16	2	1,13	4	1
Q12	2,66	2,5	1,05	5	1
Q13	2,75	3	1,26	5	1
Q14	3,16	3	1,43	6	1

does not need to study the profile of the users to develop different versions, the users themselves will develop their own version with MAWA.

- Q3 User effort: Subject's opinion is that MAWA helps personalizing any website to end-user's needs in an effortless manner. The average value to this topic has been 2,45 with a median of 2 and a maximum value of 6 and a minimum of 1.
- Q4 Small screen: subjects believe that MAWA helps browsing despite the small screen size. It is impossible to augment the screen size by a browser extension. However, the overall functionality of MAWA alleviates this drawback. The general opinion score is 1,62 with a median of 1 a maximum value of 3 and a minimum of 1.
- Q5 Scroll: subjects consider that MAWA extension avoids scrolling. Moving content from the bottom to the top of the website, avoids this common action. Their opinion is 1,71 with a median of 1 a maximum of 4 and a minimum of 1.
- Q6 Taps: Adding content from different resources, provokes that the user reduces the number of taps he carries out in his browsing activity. Participants of the evaluation agree with this statement because they think with an average value of 2,37 that this statement is true. The median is 2, the maximum value 5 and the minimum 1.
- Q7 Tab-switching: this a very common action in web activities because usually, the information needed is divided in different websites. If the user desires to obtain a complete information, he must continuously tab-switching. Participants claim that MAWA avoids tab-switching. Adding the necessary information from different websites to a single one, avoids this action because all the information is in the same site. Subjects' opinion to this statement is 1,58 with a median of 1,5, a maximum value of 3 and a minimum of 1.
- Q8 Branching: is an action related with tab-switching. Before tab-switching, the user must open a new tab. For the same reason, adding content from different websites in a single one, avoids opening new tabs. Subjects also

agree with this statement because their overall opinion is 2,12 with a median of 2. The maximum value is 4 and the minimum 1.

- Q9 URL typing: if the user must not open a new tab to obtain the information, he must write new website directions. Due to this, mistakes will not occur in the URL typing. Despite the fact that the subjects' opinion is one of the most elevated in this topic, participants also agree with this statement (AVG 2,79, median 3, minimum 1 and maximum value 5).
- Q10 Battery consumption: taking into account that screen brightness affects deeply to the battery life expectancy and overall the screen use [64], reducing the time a user has a screen lit is mandatory. In the quantitative evaluation it has been demonstrated that MAWA executes the web action faster, hence, the screen use will be reduced. Participants affirm this statement and they think that MAWA reduces the battery consumption (AVG 2,71, median 3, minimum 1 and maximum 6).
- Q11 Time: the faster is an activity performed, the better for users. They will have more time for an additional activity. Users claim that MAWA reduces the time needed to complete a web activity with an overall opinion of 2,16, a median of 2, a minimum value of 1 and a maximum of 4.
- Q12 Produce cluttered navigation: reorganizing the website is one of the main objectives of MAWA. In the subjects' opinion, MAWA reduces the cluttered navigation (AVG 2,66, median 2,5, minimum value 1 and maximum 5).
- Q13 Show unnecessary content and hide important content: RWD hides some content that is visible in the desktop computer version. In addition, it maintains some unnecessary information for some users. Removing this content is a feature of MAWA. This might be the reason why subjects think that the extension helps to remove unnecessary content and show important one (AVG 2,75, median 3, minimum 1 and maximum value 5).
- Q14 Computational cost reordering content: RWD has a computational cost to reorganize all the content. Moving, removing and adding content has also a computational cost such as it has been demonstrated in the quantitative evaluation. This statement has been the most elevated for subjects (AVG 3,16, median 3, minimum 1 and maximum 6). This affirms that users believe that MAWA does not significantly increment the computational cost.

The standard deviation of all values of the questionnaire are close to the 1 value. This means that all subjects' opinion are similar. Question 7, the one related to tab-switching, has the lowest value. Having a median of 1,5, this means that most of the values have been 1 or 2 in this issue. The most elevated standard deviation value is in question 14, the one related to the mobile computational cost. Taking into account that the computational cost is increased with the use of MAWA, the subjects' opinion might be more diverse. Some may think that MAWA reduces the computational cost and others the opposite.

4.3 Discussion

Our main objective with MAWA was to develop a tool that would alleviate all the causes and consequences of the problem described in section 2 as well as improve its usability. To check if we have met the objective, different evaluations have been carried out, some quantitative and some qualitative. Among the quantitative evaluations, 3 different tests have been performed. The first one was to check if MAWA helps to reduce battery consumption. The test shows that MAWA greatly reduces battery consumption. The weakness of this evaluation is that it has only been tested with one example, the one described in the article, and it is possible that in all cases, the reduction of consumption might vary. However, it is proven that MAWA reduces the battery consumption by alleviating this consequence. The second test consisted in checking the computational cost reordering content. In all WA tools the computational cost reordering content is increased. The evaluation shows an increase of 9.3%, a total of 76.25ms, which is an increase not perceptible by the user. As in the previous test, this evaluation has been carried out with a single example but no significant changes would be presented in other examples since this reordering is done in a single step in all cases. Finally, the third test consisted of evaluating 5 different use cases and testing the number of actions with and without MAWA. This evaluation shows that the number of actions by the user is drastically reduced with the use of MAWA. Moreover, the number of tab-switching, branching and URL typing is reduced to zero and the number of taps is almost zero. Scrolling is the only action that has been used but its reduction is significant. The total reduction of actions was 95.39% which shows that MAWA is useful for user action reduction. This test also shows a significant time reduction (84.83%) when the user is to consume the desired content. This third test reinforces the first two tests that had only been tested with one case. These new cases corroborate battery reduction and computational cost reordering content. The average reduction of battery of all the examples run is 92.75%, a value even higher than the one shown in the first test. The increase of the computational cost reordering content was 9.18%, a value very similar to the second test of the quantitative evaluation. Although 5 use cases are not a large number of cases to evaluate, all cases very similar results considering the experiments are of different nature and characteristics. We consider that this number of use cases are representative and have not conducted further tests. The entire quantitative evaluation shows that MAWA alleviates the consequences of the section 2 except for cluttered navigation and show unnecessary content and hide important content which are tested in the qualitative evaluation.

The qualitative evaluation consists of two distinct tests. One is to demonstrate that end-users perceive MAWA alleviates the consequences of the section 2. The second qualitative test determines whether MAWA is usable for end-users. The same end-user test has been used to evaluate both. The PSSUQ survey was used to assess usability. More than 75% of the subjects rated all questions below 4, the mean value of the scale. Additionally, the median of all questions

is 3 or below. This shows that users perceive MAWA as usable for end-users. On the other hand, users have been asked whether they perceive that MAWA alleviates all consequences and prevents the causes. The results collected show that their perception is that MAWA alleviates the consequences and serves to prevent the causes. The disadvantage of this evaluation is that end-users would not know as well as a developer whether the causes of cost effective, not easy to foresee, user effort and small screen would be prevented by MAWA. Although we wanted to know their opinion, it is not an objective of MAWA. However, their perception on the consequences not evaluated in the quantitative part (produce cluttered navigation and show unnecessary content and hide important content) is to be taken into account. We have considered end-users' opinion and this is positive. These users endorse the improvements that MAWA produces in these aspects and refute the consequences evaluated in the quantitative part.

5 Related work

5.1 Layout adaptation

As defined by Bouvin [7], WA modifications can be applied to website content, layout or behaviour. Some tools have been designed to impact only the layout. For example, CrowdAdapt [65] main objective is to allow end-users to adapt the interface to their desires or needs if they consider it is inadequate by the current web page design. CrowdAdapt provides a visual design environment that augments web pages loaded in the browser to allow users to customise the layout. The changes are deployed on a server in the form of a new layout template which will be automatically downloaded by the browser. This modifications can be immediately shared with other users. UIWear [66] is a client side tool that helps end-users easily create layout modifications without application source code. UIWear extracts the elements that are composed in the layout automatically. Afterwards, the user can compose the interface based on his preferences by dragging and dropping. W3touch [67] is built using jQuery for the client and PHP with MySQL on the server. W3Touch has been designed to leave the control with web designers and permit end-users to improve the layout visualization. It permits making zoom to the most desired elements of the website in order to improve their visualization due to reading problems. This modification is carried out simply tapping and selecting modifiable elements on the device screen. PageTailor [68] is a plugin that runs on Windows Mobile PDAs and is based on the Firefox browser. The tool has a technique for selecting objects that involves dragging a line over the object to choose the corresponding web node. PageTailor allows traditional websites to be customized by the size of important web elements while reducing the size of irrelevant information. PageTailor is not used in websites that implement Responsive Web Design. Since Collapse-to-Zoom [69] only allows expanding and collapsing web objects, it is a much simpler tool than PageTailor. It can also be used to make changes to conventional websites on PDAs. The node is

extended when the user taps over an element and drags the pen diagonally to the end. The element is collapsed if the movement is towards the bottom.

5.2 Layout and content adaptation

Nonetheless, some other tools have been designed to have impact not only in the layout, but also in the content. For example, SAM [70] is a client-side framework that permits the adaptation of website menus by end-users. It allows changing the style and the order of menus personalizing it for end-users to have better accessibility to the most visited sections. SAM focuses only on the menus of the web pages and MAWA allows to reorder not only menus but the whole web page. MAWA does not perform style modifications such color or font changes. W3Touch, PageTailor and Collapse-to-Zoom modify the size of the nodes of a web page making them bigger or smaller (in this way they could be considered to be removed). PageTailor and Collapse-to-Zoom are designed for PDAs and traditional web pages, i.e. without Responsive Web Design. MAWA does not allow to change the size of the nodes but enables their removal if necessary. UIWear allows to reorganize the content of a web page as MAWA does. The difference is that the selection of the nodes is done automatically and the user decides the order of the nodes and which nodes are not included (this action is like deleting them). CrowdAdapt is a server-side tool which makes it different from MAWA. This application allows to reorganize the content as MAWA does. CrowdAdapt also allows to change the size and font and even transform the text to two columns, actions not allowed in MAWA.

5.3 Content adaptation

Modifying or adding content from different resources is a common functionality in WA tools. Trusty et al. [71] developed ALOE. ALOE is a Firefox browser extension that enhances Web pages by converting all selected English words into their respective language translations. Sticklet [72] is a Firefox browser extension that allows adding content from external websites in order to enhance the content of the target web page. A Domain Specific Language (DSL) has been created to carry out this process that facilitates users with no or few programming knowledge to create their sticks. A debugger has also been implemented, which helps the designer of the augmentation to correct the mistakes. Finally, the designer can share his creations with the community. ENIA [73] displays a tool that proposes a data acquisition scheme capable of capturing web interface user interaction. Following that, these experiences can be replicated automatically without the need for human intervention, which can be a useful way to shorten the time it takes to complete a task. Similarly, Excore [24] is a program that adds content to a website based on a series of web searches. It detects a keyword on a specific website, performs

a web search on a different website, and then inserts the requested content on the target site. An end-user defines the automation through a visual programmable Chrome browser extension. By assisting users with suggestions and automated composition, Chudnosky et al. [74] take a step forward in the development of web adaptations developing Omelette. It provides end-users with a composition environment comprised of various elements that can be put on the canvas, synchronized with one another, and shared with other users. ALOE differs from MAWA in that it focuses on the translation of content into other languages exclusively. ENIA and Excore are Capture and Replay tools that repeat all the actions performed by the user automatically and obtain the information required by the user. MAWA does not repeat any user action, MAWA accesses the required content in a single step. Omelette allows inserting predefined elements and user's own content. Sticklet allows inserting content from other pages as MAWA does. The big difference is that MAWA is a Visual Programming tool and Sticklet is a DSL whose language must be learned to be used. By means of a guide, Sticklet allows users without computer knowledge to create their own sticks. These sticks are embedded as notes on a board that the user can see by clicking on them.

5.4 Content and behaviour adaptation

Not only is content adapted by WA tools, but also new behaviour is added. CrowdMock [75] is a Firefox extension. It differentiates between the developers and the consumers. The first ones create the augmentation and they share their creations with the consumers. Additionally, developers can create their augmentations collaboratively. Besides adding content from different resources, it allows adding new behaviour to the website that facilitates the navigation between different websites. MoWA [6] is a mobile browser extension that adds details to existing Web Applications that the original web page lacks. It adjusts the website content based on data collected from mobile sensors (GPS, microphone, gyroscope, light...). WebMakeup [76] is a Chrome browser extension for visual programming. Different web nodes can be copied by clicking on them with the mouse. Users will drag and drop previously copied nodes from a "Piggybank" into a website. Inserting this foreign widgets, the extension permits to change the site. WebMakeup allows you to update embedded nodes with real data or not. Furthermore, inserted nodes can be collapsed by clicking on a user-defined node. MDWA [77] introduces a novel client-side and server-side component-based approach for developing WA applications. They suggest a model-driven approach to client-side and server-side creation that can increase the abstraction level. They provide a set of tools to design the composition of core applications. These apps provide new back-end features to help with WA. The main purpose of the front-end is to enhance the web page.

These last tools perform different to MAWA since they act on the behavior of the web page. MAWA does not change or add new behavior to the web page.

Focusing on content modifications, MDWA and CrowdMock allow the user to add elements already predefined by the system as Omelette does. MAWA does not have any predefined element. MDWA also allows to add content from other pages but it never updates its content. MDWA makes simple copies of HTML and CSS. MoWA adds information based on sensors such as GPS and adds information to a given web page depending on the location. This application focuses on pages such as museums or zoos. WebMakeup allows to insert content from other pages. This content can be dynamic using iframes, static through HTML and CSS copies (no updates of content allowed) and static-dynamic whose content is changed based on certain content of the page (like looking up the rating of a certain movie in different sources). MAWA adds static content that can be updated if the user wants but does not allow dynamic content to be added.

5.5 Behaviour adaptation

Finally, some WA only include behaviour modifications or addition. For example, to define the required native input, OFIE [78] uses Programming by Demonstration, which must be implemented automatically when the rule is triggered. This approach enables end-users to identify operations by simply executing the necessary native input interactions on the application's graphical user interface. The end-user is not required to have any programming experience or to write or modify any code. Cowpath [25] is a Firefox browser extension that through a Domain Specific Language permits the creation of a "path" that connects related websites. The developer connects related web pages on a topic one with each other including a button that after clicking on it, loads a new website related with the previous one. Finally, developments can be shared in social networks with other users. The change or inclusion of behavior by MAWA is not contemplated, which makes OFIE and Cowpath very different tools compared to MAWA.

In summary, table 5 shows the characteristics of the presented tools. These tools have been developed mainly for two different platforms, mobile devices (8 tools) and desktops (9 tools). Most of the tools are client-side applications that are installed in the browser as a plug-in or extension or simply tools installed in the client. MDWA and W3touch implement a hybrid approach in which they need both a client and a server side application to be executed. CrowdAdapt is the only tool deployed on a server. Regarding collaborative development, CrowdMock and MDWA have implemented a method that permits augmentation development in a collaborative way with other users. Additionally, they allow sharing these creations with other users. Despite the fact that other tools do not allow collaborative development, they have implemented methods to share their creations with other users. WA tools draw on a variety of programming paradigms: visual languages, spreadsheets, programming by demonstration, domain specific languages (DSL) and model-based automation

Table 5 Web Augmentation tools classification

Name	Platform	Execution mode	Subject of adaptation	Collaborative	Programming paradigm	Reference
CrowdAdapt	Mobile	Server	Layout	Share with other	Programming by demonstration	[65]
UIWear	Mobile	Client	Layout	NO	Visual programming	[66]
W3touch	Mobile	Client-Server	Layout	NO	Visual programming	[67]
PageTailor	Mobile	Client	Layout	Share with other	Programming by demonstration	[68]
Collapse-to-Zoom	Mobile	Client	Layout	NO	Programming by demonstration	[69]
SAM	Mobile	Client	Layout Content	NO	Programming by demonstration	[70]
ALOE	Desktop	Client	Content	NO	Visual programming	[71]
Sticklet	Desktop	Client	Content	Share with other	DSL	[72]
ENIA	Desktop	Client	Content	Share with other	Visual programming	[73]
Excore	Desktop	Client	Content	NO	Visual programming	[24]
Omelette	Desktop	Client	Content	Share with other	Visual programming	[74]
CrowdMock	Desktop	Client	Content Behaviour	Collaborative development and sharing	Visual programming	[75]
MoWA	Mobile	Client	Content Behaviour	Share with other	Visual programming	[6]
WebMakeup	Desktop	Client	Content Behaviour	Share with other	Visual programming	[76]
MDWA	Desktop	Client-Server	Content Behaviour	Collaborative development and sharing	Visual programming	[77]
OFIE	Mobile	Client	Behaviour	Share with other	Programming by demonstration	[78]
Cowpath	Desktop	Client	Behaviour	Share with other	DSL	[25]
MAWA	Mobile	Client	Layout Content	NO	Visual programming	-

[79]. Only Sticklet and Cowpath have created a DSL that permits WA creations. Programming by demonstrations is the second most used paradigm, although visual programming is the most popular.

Independently of the target platform of these applications, the execution mode, the subject of adaptation or programming paradigm, their ultimate objective is to allow users to adapt their favourite website to their needs. Our approach, MAWA focuses on mobile browsing and it is implemented as a Firefox extension (client-side). It is a visual programming tool whose main objective is to facilitate the browsing experience of end-users by adapting the layout of websites to their needs and adding content from third-party websites via WA. All WA applications that change the layout are for mobile. This reflects the importance of the users' need to adapt them to their requirements.

6 Conclusions and future work

The growth in the number of mobile browser users has obliged web developers to design websites and make them adaptable to the screen resolution. The problem is that this adaptation is not free and developers are still designing for desktop first. This is the reason why mobile users feel harmed in mobile browsing. The causes are the impossibility of having a different version of the same website for each user, and end-users not being able to adapt their favourite websites' coding. Moreover, the small screen resolution complicates web interactions. The consequence is that users perform more scrolling, taps, branching and tab-switching. Furthermore, the time required to complete the action is more elevated and the consequence is that the battery consumption is heightened.

In order to solve these disadvantages, we have introduced MAWA, a Firefox mobile browser extension that permits reordering any websites and adding content from different resources. The main features are to remove unnecessary content, move content in order to avoid scrolling and add content. This content may be static because the required information is always the same, although it can be automatically updated if that option is selected during the edition. This second option will replace the updated external content into the corresponding element.

An evaluation has been carried out to ensure that MAWA mitigates or resolves the mobile browsing drawbacks. First, a quantitative evaluation has been performed. In this evaluation we have demonstrated that MAWA reduces battery consumption by 87,6% and that users interactions (scrolling, tapping, branching etc.) are reduced by 95,39% reducing the time needed to complete actions by 92,75%. Nonetheless, MAWA increments the computational cost by 9,18%, which is affordable considering the previous improvements. As for the qualitative evaluation, a usability questionnaire was first accomplished. The subjects affirm that MAWA is very easy to use and easy to learn. For the evaluation, the PSSUQ questionnaire has been used which shows that the system quality, information quality and interface quality of MAWA are very adequate. Finally,

the causes and consequences described in the section 2 have been evaluated. Improving the screen size is impossible for a browser extension, nevertheless, the subjects claim that MAWA helps to solve all these issues. MAWA increases the computational cost but the increase (9,18%) is not considered a major drawback according to the interviewed participants.

In the future, we contemplate developing a debugging assistant that would facilitate end-user debugging of the resulting applications. The aim of this assistant would be to help end-users to detect failures and the reason why they have happened. Moreover, MAWA assistant would help end-users to repair the malfunctions.

Another enhancement would be sharing augmentations with other MAWA users. This feature might be essential for increasing the usage of the extension. Adding a new button to MAWA's menu would be the option to upload the basic information of the augmentation to a repository. This augmentation would be downloaded to reproduce the augmentation in another browser. This feature would allow the creation of a MAWA community. Debugging features would help to customize another member's augmentations to adapt them to the user's needs.

We would also like this extension to be used on Android. Today Android does not allow extensions to be installed, but there would be a predisposition to add this option in the future. If, as in desktop computer browsers, the extensions are compatible for both browsers, the adaptation work will be minimal. Android is used by 65%⁶ of users which might make MAWA much more used. Website upgrades are the major drawback for WA tools, since nodes might no longer be found. Based on [80][81][82], the idea would be to create a mechanism capable of regenerating Xpaths for WA tools. When one of the Xpaths does not find the element, the algorithm would be able to use the information from the previous node to repair the broken Xpaths.

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Conflict of Interest

The authors declare that they have no conflict of interest.

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